

Review Article

Barriers and Facilitators to the Implementation of Green Human Resource Management in Organisations

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Abstract

The increasing environmental challenges organisations face highlights the importance of adopting sustainable practices, including Green Human Resource Management (GHRM), to promote organizational sustainability. However, the effective implementation of GHRM often encounters various obstacles. This integrative review explores these challenges and identifies key facilitators that can support successful GHRM adoption. A comprehensive literature review was conducted utilizing leading academic databases such as Google Scholar, Scopus, Emerald, Wiley, ResearchGate, ScienceDirect, and SAGE. The findings reveal that, while organizational barriers to GHRM implementation exist, identifying and leveraging essential facilitators can significantly enhance GHRM effectiveness. Theoretically, this study underscores that organizations which do not incorporate environmental objectives into their HR strategies may struggle to develop effective GHRM practices. Additionally, integrating learning and innovation into GHRM initiatives increases the likelihood of achieving sustainability goals, emphasizing the importance of continuous improvement for long-term success. Practically, organizations should consider implementing awareness programs targeted at senior leadership, embedding sustainability metrics into performance evaluations, and investing in cost-effective HR technologies that support environmentally responsible practices. Addressing these areas can promote broader GHRM adoption, contributing to environmental stewardship and organizational resilience.

Keywords: Environmental sustainability, green human resource management, green recruitment and selection, green compensation and rewards, green training and development.

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Introduction

Over the past fifty years, numerous organizations involved in international trade have encountered challenges related to their environmental performance. The adoption of preventative measures and chemical interventions can significantly mitigate issues such as climate change, environmental degradation, the release of various toxins into the air and water, noise and visual pollution, and the decline of wildlife populations (Billig et al., 2022; Darvishmotevali and Altınay, 2022). Furthermore, businesses are currently witnessing a heightened awareness of environmental issues. Businesses and consumers across various sectors are increasingly committed to sustainability efforts. As climate change and its associated financial and social consequences present substantial challenges, addressing environmental degradation has emerged as a critical priority for organizations. This urgency has prompted businesses to proactively engage in initiatives aimed at enhancing their environmental practices. One prominent approach is GHRM, which is widely recognized as an effective strategy for promoting organizational sustainability, although it does face challenges in its implementation. Jangra, & Gupta, (2021) state that GHRM practices encounter several implementation challenges within organizations. Common obstacles include inadequate incentives, limited awareness, and lack of effective planning. In small and medium-sized enterprises, barriers such as high implementation costs, technological intricacies, and employee resistance impede the adoption of GHRM (Shrestha et al., 2022). The banking sector faces difficulties related to outdated technology, substantial initial investments, and insufficiently effective policies (Shakir, & Khan, 2023). The size of the organization affects GHRM implementation; while larger firms generally possess more resources, they may also encounter greater complexity.

Literature Review

Sulistiawan, Herachwati, and Khansa (2024) here view through barriers, whereas (Rana & Arya, 2024) postulate thoughts on the importance of GHRM, the importance and barriers are viewed in this discussion on a different focus.

According to Fazlurrahman, Rahman, and Arifah (2021), GHRM practices can reduce an organisation's environmental impact and improve corporate social responsibility. As a result, the concept of GHRM has gained significant attention among researchers and organisational management over the years.

Definition of Green Human Resource Management

To foster environmental stewardship, organizations are actively working to integrate and strengthen environmental philosophy within their corporate culture through the implementation of GHRM. According to Masri and Jaaron (2017), GHRM emphasizes the utilization of human resource management practices to cultivate an environmental culture and encourage employee accountability regarding sustainability efforts. Additionally, Al-Romeedy (2019) identified key GHRM practices, which include green job analysis and definition, green recruitment and selection, green job management, training focused on sustainability, and green rewards and compensation. Opatha and Arulrajah (2014) further contributed to this discussion by providing a comprehensive

definition of GHRM, describing it as a model dedicated to developing a green workforce that benefits employees, society, and the business sector.

Importance of Green Human Resource Management

Green management and environmental management have emerged as critical components of corporate strategy, garnering significant recognition among organizations (Ullah, 2017). It is important to highlight that a well-regarded corporate strategy relevant to management efforts in organisational greening is GHRM, which is viewed as a highly effective approach to corporate sustainability initiatives. *To strengthen the importance of GRHM in the management literature*, Jabbour and Jabbour, (2016) state that GHRM can be understood through its ability to tackle essential issues such as waste reduction, the adoption of environmentally friendly products, and energy conservation, alongside influencing employee behaviour. *In postulating the importance of GHRM*, a study conducted by Rana and Arya (2024) aimed to assess the influence of GHRM practices on enhancing employees' environmental performance (ENVP). The study gathered data from 579 individuals employed in the Indian manufacturing sector. A total of 579 employees from this industry participated in the research. The proposed model was evaluated using SMART PLS 3.3. The findings of the study indicate that GHRM is a significant predictor of environmental performance (ENVP) within the Indian economy, with Green Innovation (GI) exhibiting a partial mediating effect. The study demonstrates that GHRM practices implemented by organizations foster employee engagement in innovation, the development of sustainable products, and the exploration of new environmentally friendly methods to improve business environmental performance. Recognizing the significance of our ongoing discussions, it is crucial to highlight the role of GHRM in the implementation of environmentally sustainable human resource practices. These principles aim to enhance efficiency, reduce costs, and foster employee loyalty. This approach encourages employee participation in various initiatives such as distance learning, virtual meetings, retraining, remote work, and recruitment and training processes, prioritizing fairness and equity. Ultimately, these practices strive to enhance organizational effectiveness and efficiency while minimizing resource consumption. (Qatoush, and Majidi,2022).

Barriers to the Implementation of GHRM Practices

While the analysis of the implementation and application of GHRM in organisations is commendable, this study highlighted several challenges associated with its adoption. Research conducted by Sulistiawan, Herachwati, and Khansa (2024) explored the barriers to the implementation of GHRM, particularly within the banking sector in Indonesia, considering the element of uncertainty. The study engaged an expert panel comprising 28 professionals and two professors to provide insights. To fulfil the research objectives, the researchers employed observational analysis alongside the Delphi fuzzy and fuzzy decision-making methods. The findings identified a total of 14 patterns, including five key characteristics that significantly influence the situation. The primary challenges facing the banking sector include the absence of a green culture, scepticism regarding the benefits of green initiatives, the capability of employees to enact such changes, inadequate support from senior management, and the lack of a comprehensive strategy for green human resources management. The behaviours contributing to these challenges

are categorized into management, human resources, organizational dynamics, and customer relations.

Considering the points, Tweneboa Kodua, Xiao, Adjei, Asante, Ofori, and Amankona (2022) undertook a study aimed at examining significant challenges associated with the implementation of GHRM in businesses within Ghana. The researchers conducted preliminary interviews with 20 professionals in human resource and environmental management to pre-test the survey items. Subsequently, they distributed 119 questionnaires to key stakeholders, including CEOs (19), HR managers (30), CFOs (30), and department heads (40) from a range of companies. The analysis utilized a Selective Index (PSI) to measure both primary and secondary issues identified. The findings indicated that financial challenges represented 23.3% of the issues related to GHRM in the study, with the lack of financial resources being the most critical concern, yielding the highest assessment value of 0.999. Additionally, political and administrative management issues accounted for 20.1% of the challenges, while cultural and educational factors were prioritized among the key problems, constituting 18.2%. Moreover, a study conducted by Bombiak (2020) identified the primary obstacles to the adoption of GHRM strategies in Polish companies. This study, conducted in 2018, evaluated a random sample of 300 Polish companies, engaging managers responsible for the development of HR policies. The research employed computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI). In the initial phase of the analysis, the level of GHRM implementation across seven workplaces was assessed using a 5-point Likert scale. The subsequent phase aimed to identify key issues impacting the implementation of GHRM practices. The findings revealed that the principal barriers to implementing GHRM included limited budgeting, insufficient motivation to advocate for sustainable environmental practices, inadequate management of human health, ineffective GHRM tools, and challenging organizational culture.

The ongoing discussions surrounding the challenges associated with implementing GHRM have highlighted that the barriers to its adoption differ significantly between developed and developing countries. Kodua et al., (2022) state that in developing nations, the primary challenges stem from economic constraints, notably a lack of financial resources. Additionally, political, regulatory, cultural, and educational factors further complicate the implementation of GHRM in these regions. In contrast, developed countries encounter challenges including limited financial resources, insufficient incentives, low management competencies, perceived ineffectiveness of GHRM tools, and a cultural emphasis on economic values (Bombiak, 2020). According to Fayyazi et al. (2015), the oil industry faces significant challenges due to the lack of a comprehensive plan and the ambiguity surrounding green values.

Enablers to the Implementation of GHRM Practices

The study contributes to the literature on GHRM in many ways. Research on barriers and facilitators of GHRM implementation significantly enriches the existing body of knowledge by offering a complete framework for both theoretical and empirical investigation. Based on the current discussion, this phase of the study offers valuable insights into the facilitators of implementing GHRM. Consistent with the previous assertion, Hussain (2018) highlights that green recruiting and selection play a significant role in enhancing a firm's sustainability by promoting the cultivation of an

environmentally conscious workforce. Pham et al., (2019) suggest that green recruitment and selection refers to the process of recruiting and selecting candidates, particularly those who demonstrate knowledge and awareness of environmental issues and are concerned about them. During green recruitment and selection, it is worthwhile communicating about the company's environmental values and orientation programs (Pham & Paillé, 2020). Green leadership behaviours and styles assist in ensuring that integrated environmental conditions can be put in proper and appropriate shape (Li et al., 2020). They have a strong opinion that green leaders must have stronger environmental values than those who belong to other types of environments (Peng et al., 2020). Opatha and Arulrajah (2014) argued that training and development is a crucial factor that develops an awareness to adopt GHRM practices. Suharti and Sugiarto (2020) indicated that organizations should provide the best training programs for the existing staff to support the effective implementation of GHRM practices. Green compensation and rewards are a system of financial and non-financial rewards that align with a strategic approach that aims to motivate, secure and inspire employees to support environmental goals (Jabbour et al., 2013). According to Veleva and Ellenbecker (2001), green compensation and rewards lead to a sense of pride among co-workers effectively and encourage environmental behaviours. The motivational aspect of the implementation process can be enhanced through the introduction of a green pay initiative and corresponding reward system, which can encourage employees to increase their productivity within the organization (Masri & Jaaron, 2017). Govindarajulu and Daily (2004) emphasized that support from top management is a significant enabler affecting the implementation of GHRM practices. They emphasized that the successful adoption of GHRM concepts relies heavily on the vision and backing of senior management. Consequently, to facilitate the implementation of GHRM initiatives, management needs to allocate appropriate resources and develop effective strategies, as these are critical factors in the successful integration of GHRM within organizations, positively impacting both environmental management and organizational performance (Daily & Huang, 2001).

The effective implementation of GHRM practices within sectors is supported by a variety of organizational and individual facilitators. For example, in the manufacturing sector, Key factors contributing to this include government environmental policies, strong green leadership, top management support, and a focus on green health and safety (Ansari et al., 2024). GHRM practices such as recruitment, training, performance appraisal, and incentive programs play a crucial role in fostering a green organizational culture, which in turn enhances environmental performance (Roscoe et al., 2019). Additionally, important enablers include the energy and resource crisis, competitive advantages, availability of financial and human resources, and effective green supplier management (Mittal et al., 2018). Notably, the commitment of top management, green procurement initiatives, and societal concerns regarding environmental protection are recognized as the most significant enablers, while competitiveness and access to clean technology carry comparatively less weight (Toke & Kalpande, 2017). Understanding these enablers and their interrelationships is essential for organizations seeking to develop effective GHRM implementation strategies, thereby improving environmental performance and promoting sustainable development (Ansari et al., 2024; Roscoe et al., 2019).

Research Methodology

This study employs an integrative literature review technique to assess, analyse, and identify the barriers and facilitators to the implementation of GHRM practices within organizations. Cronin and George (2023) highlighted that an integrative review can yield valuable insights regarding the current state of research on a particular topic and guide future inquiries. This methodology is pertinent to the study as it rigorously examines primary research that incorporates multiple methods.

Research Strategy

The research centres on peer-reviewed articles that examine the challenges and facilitators related to Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) practices. In this context, articles were obtained from online databases, including Google Scholar and Scopus. Additional journals were sourced from various platforms such as Emerald, Wiley, ResearchGate, ScienceDirect, and SAGE.

Article Selection Criteria

In conducting an integrative review, the reliability and validity of the study depend on the quality of the selected sources. This review specifically focused on peer-reviewed articles published in reputable journals, while excluding books and non-refereed articles. It included all research-based studies, encompassing both original research and review articles. For inclusion and exclusion criteria, only articles related to the barriers and facilitators of GHRM were included, while those that did not address these factors were excluded from the analysis.

Results

Findings from the review postulate insight into the concept and significance of green human resource management (GHRM) affirming that as a concept it integrates environmental sustainability into HR practices, fostering eco-conscious behaviours among employees while enhancing organisational and societal benefits. Key scholars define GHRM as a strategic framework encompassing:

- Green recruitment & selection – Hiring employees aligned with sustainability values (Al-Romeedy, 2019).
- Green training & development – Equipping staff with skills for sustainable practices (Opatha & Arulrajah, 2014).
- Green performance management & rewards – Incentivizing eco-friendly behaviours (Cherif, 2023; Jabbour & Jabbour, 2016).
- Policy development – Structuring HR practices to reduce waste and energy consumption (Qatoush & Majidi, 2022).

GHRM enhances environmental performance (ENVP) and drives green innovation (GI), particularly in emerging economies like India (Rana & Arya, 2024). It also strengthens corporate reputation, job satisfaction, and operational efficiency (Yin, 2023; Muster & Schrader, 2011).

Synthesised Conceptual Overview of Barriers and Facilitators to GHRM Implementation

The implementation of GHRM is influenced by various barriers and facilitators, which determine its success in organisations. This framework synthesizes key findings from the literature, categorizing factors that hinder or support GHRM adoption.

Key Barriers to GHRM Implementation

1. Organizational Culture & Awareness

- Lack of green organizational culture
- Limited understanding of GHRM concepts
- Resistance to change among employees

2. Economic & Resource Constraints

- Insufficient financial resources
- Lack of incentives for green practices
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3. Leadership & Policy Issues

- Inadequate top management support
- Weak institutional commitment to GHRM policies

4. Regulatory & Educational Gaps

- Political and regulatory obstacles
- Lack of training and competencies in sustainability

Key Facilitators of GHRM Implementation

1. Green Recruitment & Selection

- Hiring environmentally conscious employees
- Aligning recruitment with organizational sustainability values

2. Green Leadership & Management Support.

- Strong commitment from top management
- Visionary leadership promoting sustainability

3. Training & Development

- High-quality environmental training programs
- Enhancing employee skills in sustainable HRM

4. **Motivational & Reward Systems**

- Green pay initiatives and incentives
- Recognition for eco-friendly performance

SUCCESSFUL GHRM IMPLEMENTATION

- Improved environmental performance
- Enhanced corporate reputation
- Sustainable organisational culture

The framework highlights the challenges organizations must overcome by identifying key barriers while also providing strategies to counteract these obstacles through facilitators. Successful implementation of GHRM leads to positive environmental and organisational outcomes, such as reduced waste and improved sustainability performance. By outlining both barriers and facilitators, this framework serves as a practical guide for organizations to identify obstacles and leverage enablers, ensuring effective integration of GHRM practices. Ultimately, it supports businesses in achieving their sustainability goals while enhancing operational efficiency.

Conclusion

The existing literature indicates that over the past fifty years, organizations engaged in international trade have faced increasing environmental challenges, prompting a proactive approach toward sustainable business practices. Consequently, Green Human Resource Management (GHRM) has emerged as a vital strategy to foster environmental responsibility, enhance corporate social responsibility, and support organizational sustainability. Research demonstrates that GHRM practices—such as green recruitment, training, performance management, and incentive systems—play a crucial role in reducing environmental impacts, fostering innovation, and increasing employee engagement in sustainability efforts. While implementing GHRM may present certain challenges, identifying key enablers can facilitate successful integration. These insights emphasize the importance of incorporating GHRM into corporate strategies to address environmental concerns, ensure compliance with regulations, and strengthen long-term competitive advantage.

Implications

Theoretical Implications

The objective of this study is to examine the barriers and facilitators associated with the implementation of GHRM within organizations. The findings from the literature review indicate that while there are challenges connected to the implementation of GHRM, there are also opportunities for successful integration. Consequently, the theoretical implication is that organizations that do not incorporate environmental objectives into their GHRM initiatives may struggle to effectively develop or execute successful GHRM practices. Additionally, it is acknowledged that companies that integrate learning and innovation into their GHRM processes are more likely to achieve both environmental and organisational objectives.

Practical Implications

Taking into consideration the aim of the study, the practical implications for the study are that organizational management must be able to facilitate awareness meetings for senior management, integrate sustainability metrics into leadership evaluations, and invest in HR technology that promotes environmentally friendly practices while minimizing capital expenditure.

Future Researches

Future researches should prioritize the development of sector-specific GHRM frameworks and strategies to address implementation challenges, thereby enhancing organizations' capacity to contribute to global sustainability goals. Ultimately, GHRM constitutes a transformative approach that integrates human resource practices with environmental responsibility, providing advantages for organizations, employees, and society.

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